

Awareness on Education Software and Its Utilization among Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract:

Today technology is being included as an integral part of education system in India and so role of teachers is vital in this regard. This study intends to find out the Awareness on Education Software and its Utilization among Secondary School Teachers. Survey Method was used for this study. The study was conducted on a sample of 200 Secondary School Teachers in Kozhikode district of Kerala State. Stratified random sampling technique was used to collect data from Secondary School Teachers. The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques. The findings of the Study revealed that Majority of the Secondary School Teachers have an average level of Awareness on Education software and its Utilizations.

Keywords: Awareness, Education Software, Utilization, Secondary School Teachers.

Introduction:

Today technology is being included as an integral part of education system in India and so role of teachers is vital in this regard. Hence a good knowledge about Educational software among teachers improves the quality of learning process. Multimedia content such as graphics, pictures, and sound help to engage students in the class. Students can collaborate on group projects using technology-based tools such as wikis and Google docs

Today, massive amounts of information (books, audio, images, videos) are available at one's fingertips through the Internet, and opportunities for formal learning are available online. worldwide through various Educational software such as Utility software, Special need software, Drill and practice software, Simulations, and MOOCs, podcasts, traditional online degree programs, and more. Through various Educational software, teachers are able to create interactive classes and make the lessons more enjoyable, which could improve student attendance and concentration. They can guide students through the learning process and provide them with appropriate and effective learning strategies. Virtual learning might be relatively a new concept in India, but we are experiencing a new trend of blended learning model gaining popularity. It involves a paradigm shift in pedagogy through an understanding of blended learning model by teachers, parents and students. Due to COVID-19 situation, most of the institutions have shifted to online teaching and this transition will be challenging for almost all the teachers. In this context, the awareness of Secondary school teachers on modern educational software is very important.

Need and Significance of the Study:

Education software is a broad and general term that is used in referring to all forms of software created specifically for learning processes. Online education software also includes special software

that is developed for addressing the needs of a student who has special needs. In teaching and learning, there are many ways technology can become an integral part through various Educational software, teachers are able to create interactive classes and make the lessons more enjoyable, which could improve student attendance and concentration. They must guide students through the learning process and provide them with appropriate and effective learning strategies. Education software helps students to enhance interest in their studies. They are assisting the students to become more concerned about their education.

Education software which is also helpful in enhancing the interaction between parents and teachers. So the teachers should have a deep knowledge about various Educational software and applications and should be able to assess student needs efficiently and effectively. Through tutorial software, teachers could teach students new lessons and give them a platform through which they could learn the lesson at their own pace. Education software helps students to enhance interest in their studies. They are assisting the students to become more concerned about their education. So the teachers should have a deep knowledge and through awareness about various Educational software and its applications and should be able to assess student needs efficiently and effectively. Due to COVID-19 situation, most of the institutions have shifted to online teaching and this transition will be challenging for almost all the teachers. Educational software has the capability of revolutionizing how ideas and content are created and presented to all students. It also promotes a productive learning environment. In this context, the awareness of secondary school teachers on modern educational software is very important. The present study is an attempt to investigate the level of **Awareness on**

Education Software and its Utilization among Secondary School Teachers of Kozhikode District., Therefore, the investigator think that the study is more relevant because of the technological contributions for education is grow very rapidly. All teachers and students are ready to be following blended learning process in future. So it's very important to have a wide and updated awareness among the teachers on various Educational software and applications available and to satisfy the needs of students in an effective and fruitful way.

Statement of the Problem: The present study is entitled as **Awareness on Education Software and its Utilization among Secondary School Teachers**
Definitions of the Key Terms:

The important terms used in the statement of the problem are defined as follows;

1. Education software:

Education Software is a term used for any computer software designed to do an educational purpose hence makes the part of education more effective. (Oxford learners Dictionary, 2017)

In the present study by the term "**Education Software**" the investigator means, any program made for an educational purpose which includes Computer software, Mobile applications and Online learning platforms.

2. Awareness:

Awareness means knowing something exists and is important (Oxford learners Dictionary, 2021) In the present study by the term "**Awareness** "., used to analyze the merits, demerits and understandings about various Educational Apps among Secondary school teachers

3. Utilization:

The term utilization means the usage of something, especially for a practical purpose. (Oxford learners Dictionary, 2011) In the present study the term "**Utilization** "implies the use of education software and mobile applications.

4. Secondary School Teachers:

A person who educates Secondary Level Students, typically specializing in one or more academic subjects (Encyclopedia Britannica, 1950). In the Present study, the term "**Secondary School Teachers** " include teachers taking classes in 8th , 9th and 10th standard in Kozhikode district of Kerala state.

Objectives of the Study: The Objectives of the study are;

1. To examine the level of Awareness on Education Software among Secondary school Teachers.
2. To find out the level of Utilization of Education Software among Secondary school Teachers.
3. To find out whether there exists any significant difference in the mean scores of Awareness on Education Software among the Secondary school Teachers with respect to subsamples;

- a) Locale
 - b) Type of Management
 - c) Year of Experience
4. To find whether there exists any significant difference in the mean scores of Utilization of Education Software among Secondary school Teachers with respect to subsamples;
 - a) Locale
 - b) Type of Management
 - c) Year of Experience

Hypothesis of the Study:

The Hypothesis of the study are;

1. There is an Average level of Awareness on Education Software among Secondary school Teachers.
2. There is an Average level of Utilization of Education Software among Secondary school Teachers.
3. There will be a significant difference in the level of Awareness on Education Software among Secondary school Teachers with respect to the subsamples based on
 - a) Locale
 - b) Type of Management
 - c) Year of Experience.
4. There will be a significant difference in the level of Utilization of Education Software among Secondary school Teachers with respect to subsamples based on
 - a) Locale
 - b) Type of Management
 - c) Year of Experience.

Variables of the Study: The Variables of the Study are;

Criterion Variable:

- Awareness on Education Software
- Utilization on Education Software

Classificatory Variable:

- Locale
- Type of Management
- Year of Experience

Methodology: The Methodology used for the present study is given in brief under the following heads:

Design of the study:

The present study is descriptive in nature and the Survey method is used to find out the Awareness on Education Software and its Utilization among Secondary School Teachers.

Variables of the Study:

Criterion Variable

- Awareness on Education software
- Utilization of educational software

Classificatory Variables

- Locale
- Type of management
- Year of experience

Sample for the Study:

The present study was conducted on a representative sample of 200 Secondary School Teachers of Kozhikode district in Kerala. Sample was drawn by stratified random sampling technique giving due representation to factors like Locale, Type of Management and Year of Experiences..

Tools used for the Study:

The present study was conducted by using;

1. Awareness test to find the Educational Software Awareness developed and standardized by the investigator with the help of the Supervising teacher (Abdul Rasheed Poozhithara & Nimmy C.P, 2022).
2. Utilization scale of Education Software was developed and standardized by the investigator with the help of the Supervising teacher (Abdul Rasheed Poozhithara & Nimmy C.P, 2022).

Statistical Techniques used for the Study: The Statistical techniques used for the Present study are;

- Graphical representation
- Preliminary Analysis
- Percentage Analysis
- Test of Significant difference between Means

Analysis and Interpretation:

The present study was intended to estimate the Awareness and the extent of Utilization of Educational software among Secondary School

Teachers based on 200 secondary school teachers of Kozhikode district in Kerala. The collected data was analyzed statistically to accomplish the objectives of the study. The collected data was analyzed using preliminary analysis, Percentage analysis and Test of Significance difference between Means. Data and results of statistical analysis were presented and discussed based on the objectives of the study.

Preliminary Analysis:

The variables studied in the present investigation were Awareness on Education software and Utilization of Education software among Secondary school Teachers. These variables were studied in different categories based on locale, type of management and year of experience. After the data was collected, it was classified and the data needed to be systematized, organized, edited and tabulated. . The data obtained through the administration of the awareness test towards education software and utilization scale of education software among the sample of 200 teachers of Secondary School was edited, classified and tabulated. Statistics like Mean, Median, Mode and Standard deviation for the selected two variables are computed for the whole sample (N=200) and the data are presented in **Table. 1**.

Table. 1: Summary of Mean, Median, Mode, Standard deviation, kurtosis and Kurtosis of Awareness on Education software for the Total Sample.

Sr no.	Variables	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
1	Education software awareness	20.2800	22.00	22.0	6.31513	-.802	-.146
2	Utilization of education software	91.2067	89.000	82.00	12.5143	.223	-1.002

From table.1 it is found that there is not much variance in the measurement of central tendencies viz, Mean, Median, Mode of the two variables of the study. The values of Skewness and Kurtosis in the case of variable Awareness on Education software are -.802 and -.146 respectively. This suggests that distribution of the variable

Awareness of Education software is negatively skewed and platykurtic. For the variable Utilization of Education software, the value of Skewness and Kurtosis are .223 and -1.002 respectively. This suggests that it is positively skewed and Platykurtic as kurtosis negative.

Fig 1: Histogram and normal curve of the distribution of Awareness on education software

Fig 2: Histogram and normal curve of the distribution of Utilization of education software

Major Analysis:

Level of Awareness on Education software among secondary school teachers for the total sample

Objective 1 is to find out the level of Awareness on Education software among secondary

school teachers for the total sample. To assess the level and extent of awareness on education software among secondary school teachers, investigator calculated the percentage of Awareness on education software. Data and result of Mean and standard deviation of scores is presented in **table .2**

Table. 2: Data and result of Mean and Standard deviation of scores on Awareness on education software for the total sample

Category	N	Mean	S.D
Total sample	200	20.28	6.31

From the table 2, it is observed that the Mean (M) and standard Deviation (σ) of the scores are 20.28 and 6.31 respectively. $M+\sigma$ and $M-\sigma$ were calculated to obtain the level of Awareness on Education software. $M+\sigma$ is found to be 26.59 and $M-\sigma$ is found to be 13.99. Thus those teachers whose score above 26.59 will come under High awareness level. Those teachers whose score below 13.99 will fall under Low awareness level. And

those teachers whose score in between 26.59 and 13.99 will fall under average level of awareness.

Percentage Analysis:

Percentage Analysis was made to find out the level of Awareness on education software among secondary school teachers for the total sample. The level of Awareness on Education software among Secondary school teachers is given in **Table 3.**

Table 3: Data and Result of level of Awareness on Education software among Secondary School teachers

Sl no.	Group	N	%
1	High Awareness	45	22.5%
2	Average Awareness	124	62%
3	Low Awareness	31	15.5%

The results of Table. 3 reveals that 22.5% of Secondary school teachers have High level of Awareness on Education software, 62% have Average level of Awareness on Education software

and 15.5% have Low level of Awareness on Education software.

Hence the level of Awareness on Education software among Secondary school teachers is average.

Fig 3: Level of Utilization of Education software among Secondary school teachers for the Total sample

Objective 2 is to find out the level of Utilization of Education software among Secondary school teachers for the Total sample. The Mean and

Standard Deviation for scores of Utilization of Education software for the total sample is presented in the **Table 4**

Table 4: Data and result of Mean and Standard Deviation of score on Utilization of Education software for the total sample

Sample category	N	Mean	S.D
Total sample	200	91.206	12.514

From the table 4, it is observed that the Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (σ) of the scores are 91.206 and 12.514 respectively, $M+\sigma$ and $M-\sigma$ were calculated to obtain the level of Utilization of Education software. $M+\sigma$ is found to be 103.72 and $M-\sigma$ is found to be 78.692. Thus those teachers score above 103.72 will come under High level of Utilization. Those teachers score below 78.692 will fall under Low level of Utilization. And those

teachers score in between 103.72 and 78.692 will fall under Average level of Utilization.

The Percentage Analysis was made to find out the level of Utilization among secondary school teachers for the Total sample The Utilization of Education software among Secondary School teachers is given in Ta So the teachers should have a deep knowledge about various Educational software and applications and should be able to assess student needs efficiently and effectively **table .05**

Table 05: Data and Result of level of Utilization of Education software among Secondary School teachers

Sl no.	Group	N	%
1	High Utilization	32	16%
2	Average Utilization	111	55.5%
3	Low Utilization	57	28.5%

The results of Table 05 reveals that 16% of Secondary school teachers have High level of Utilization of Education software, 55.5% have Average level Utilization of Education software and

28.5% have Low level of Utilization of Education software.

Hence the level of Utilization of education software among the Total sample of Secondary school teachers is Average.

Fig.4: Comparison of the Mean scores of Awareness on Education software among secondary school teachers with respect to subsamples

Objective 3 is to find out whether there exists any significant difference in the mean scores of Awareness on Education software among secondary School teachers with respect to subsamples a) Locale, b) Type of management, c) Year of experience.

Comparison of the mean scores of Awareness on education software among secondary school teachers with respect to Locale:

The test of significance of the difference between the mean scores of Awareness on education software among secondary school teachers with respect to Locale is given in **table 06**

Table 06: Data and result of t-test for comparing the Mean score of Awareness on education software among Secondary school teachers for the subsample based on Locale

Sample	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t	Significant level
Urban	99	21.485	5.362	2.216	0.05
Rural	101	19.225	6.904		

From table 06, it is clear that the calculated t value is 2.216 which is greater than the table value 1.96, value set for 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there exists a significant difference between Mean score of Awareness on education software among Secondary school teachers for Urban and Rural teachers

Comparison of the mean scores of Awareness on education software Based on Type of management

The test of significance of the difference between the mean scores of Awareness on Education software among secondary school teachers with respect to Type of management is given in **table 07**

Table 07: Data and result of test of significance of difference between Mean score of Awareness on education software among Secondary school teachers for the subsample based on Type of management

Sample	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t	Significant level
Aided	97	19.9231	6.50628	7.19	0.05
Government	103	20.667	6.12315		

Comparison of the mean scores of Awareness on education software Based on Year of experience:

The test of significance of the difference between the mean scores of Awareness on

Education software among secondary school teachers with respect to Year of Experience is given in **table 08**

Table 08: Data and result of test of significance of difference between Mean score of Awareness on education software among Secondary school teachers for the subsample based on Year of experience

Sample	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t	Significant level
Experience<10 years	92	20.8333	5.63940	.896	0.05
Experience>10 years	108	19.9079	6.83165		

From the table 08, it is clear that the calculated t value of Awareness on education software is .896 which is less than the table value

1.96 at 0.05 level of significance, hence there exist no significant difference in the mean score of

Awareness on education software based on the Year of experience

Comparison of the Mean scores of Utilization of Education software among secondary school teachers with respect to subsamples:

Objective 4 is to find out whether there exists any significant difference in the mean scores of Utilization of Education software among secondary school teachers with respect to

subsamples a) Locale, b) Type of management, c) Year of experience.

Comparison of the mean scores of Utilization of education software with respect to subsample Locale:

The test of significance of the difference between the mean scores of Utilization on Education software among Secondary school teachers with respect to Locale is given in **table 09**

Table 09: Data and result of test of significance of difference between mean score Utilization of education software among Secondary school teachers for the subsample based on Locale

Sample	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t	Significant level
Urban	99	92.2857	11.66705	.988	0.05
Rural	101	90.2625	13.21176		

From table 09, it is clear that the calculated t value is .988, which is less than the table value 1.96, value set for 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there exists no significant difference between Mean score of Utilization of education software among Secondary school teachers for Urban and Rural teachers.

Comparison of the mean scores of Utilization of education software Based on subsample Type of management:

The test of significance of the difference between the mean scores of Utilization on Education software among Secondary school teachers with respect to Type of management is given in **table 10**.

Table 10: Data and result of test of significance of difference between Mean score of Utilization of education software among Secondary school teachers for the subsample based on Type of management

Sample	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t	Significant level
Aided	97	91.4872	11.69498	.285	0.05
Government	103	90.9028	13.42182		

From the table 10 it is clear that the calculated t value of Utilization of education software is .285 which is less than the table value of 1.95 at 0.05 level of significance, hence there exist no significant difference in the mean score of utilization of education software based on the Type of management.

Comparison of the mean scores of Utilization of education software Based on Year of experience

The test of significance of the difference between the mean scores of Utilization on Education software among Secondary school teachers with respect to Year of Experience is given in **table 11**

Table 11: Data and result of test of significance of difference between Mean score of Utilization of education software among Secondary school teachers for the subsample based on Year of experience

Sample	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t	Significant level
Experience>10 years	108	90.2895	12.64681	.995	0.05
Experience<10 years	92	92.3472	12.48792		

From table 11, it is clear that the calculated t value of Utilization of education software is .995 which is lesser than the table value 1.95 at 0.05 level of significance, hence there exists no significant difference in the mean score of Utilization of education software based on the Year of experience.

Major Findings of the Study:

On the basis of Analysis done, the investigator has arrived at the following findings;

- Majority of the Secondary school Teachers have an Average level of Awareness on Education Software.
- Majority of the Secondary school Teachers have an Average level of Utilization of Education Software.
- There exists a significant difference in the Awareness level on Education Software among

the Secondary school Teachers based on the subsample Locale.

- There exists a significant difference in the Awareness on Education Software among the Secondary school Teachers based on the subsample Type of Management.
- There exists no significant difference in the Awareness on Education Software among the Secondary school Teachers based on the subsample Year of Experience.
- There exists no significant difference in the Utilization of Education Software among the Secondary school teachers based on the subsample Locale.
- There exists no significant difference in the Utilization on Education Software among the

Secondary school Teachers based on the subsample Type of Management.

- There exists no significant difference in the Utilization of Education Software among the Secondary school Teachers based on the subsample Year of Experience.

Conclusion:

Findings of the study depicts that there is Average level of Awareness on Education Software and its Utilization among Secondary School Teachers. It would be better to create more Awareness among the Secondary School Teachers regarding the Education Software and its Utilization. Various activities that can be done in order to develop Awareness on Education software and its Utilization among Secondary School teachers. The results reveal that, among the total sample of 200 secondary school teachers, 22.5% of teachers have a higher level of Awareness on Education software, 62% of teachers have a moderate level of Awareness on Education software and remaining 15.5% of teachers have lower level of Awareness on Education software. All these indicate that the level of Awareness on Education software among secondary school teachers is Average. The results also reveal that among the total sample of 200 Secondary school teachers, 16% teachers have a higher level of Utilization of Education software, 55.5% of teachers have a moderate level of Utilization of Education software and the remaining 28.5% teachers have a Low level of Utilization of Education software. All these indicate that the level of Utilization of Education software among Secondary school teachers is Average.

From this study, it can be concluded that the majority of secondary school teachers have an Average level of Awareness on Education software and an Average level of Utilization on Education software. So the teachers should have a deep knowledge and through awareness about various Educational software and it's applications and should be able to assess student needs efficiently and effectively. It also promotes a productive learning environment. In this context, the awareness of secondary school teachers on modern educational software and its utilization is very important. Finding of the present study would lead to a better understanding of the importance of Education software Awareness and its utilization among Secondary School Teachers. The investigator found that, the study is relevant for our present education system. Day by day the system is developing and method of teaching is transformed into online mode. The study will also help to put forward some useful ideas, views, inference, conclusions and suggestions in this regard for further observation and investigation.

References:

1. Alomari, M., & Jabr, M. (2020). The effect of the use of educational software based on the strategy of artificial intelligence on students' achievement and their attitudes towards it. *Management Science Letters*, 10(13), 2951-2960
2. Dadhe, P. P., & Patil, S. M. (2021). *An Empirical Study of Awareness and Use of ICT by School Teachers Before and During Lockdown Due to COVID-19 Pandemic*. Library Philosophy and Practice, 2021.
3. Hendawi, M., & Nosair, M. R. (2020). Students' technological awareness at the College of Education, Qatar University. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, 15(4), 749-765.
4. Niederhauser, D.S., & Stoddart, T. (2001). Teachers' instructional Perspectives and use of educational software. *Teaching and teacher Education*, 17(1), 15-31
5. Obidike, N., Anyikwa, N., & Enemou, J. O. (2010). Teachers' awareness of the existence and the use of technology to promote children's literacy instruction. *African Journal of Teacher Education*, 1(1)
6. Onasanya, S. A., Shehu, R. A., Ogunlade, O. O., & Adefuye, A. L. (2011) Teacher's awareness and extent of utilization of information Communication technologies for effective science and health education in Nigeria. *Singapore Journal of Scientific Research*, 1(1), 49-58.
7. Paris, P.G. (2004). E-Learning: A Study on Secondary Students' Attitudes towards Online Web Assisted Learning. *International Education Journal*, 5(1), 98-112.
8. M. J Philomina, M. J., & Amritha. S., (2016) Information and Communication Technology Awareness among Teacher Educators. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology* Vol.6 No.8
9. Sharma, K., & Chaudhary, M. A. *Education Technology: Awareness among teachers for enhanced learning outcome*
10. Wegerif, R. (2004). *The role of educational software as a support for teaching and learning conversations*. *Computers & Education*, 43(1-2), 179-191.